

INTERFERENCE, HOMONYMY AND WORD ASSOCIATIONS *

PETRANKA T. IVANOVA

Abstract: *Some discrepancies between articulation of sounds in Bulgarian and in English might be the reason for Bulgarian learners of English to mishear an English word. The failure to identify the correct phoneme leads to wrong interpretations of what is being said and in case of a type of a free association test due to homonymy the response words go in completely different directions. Interference is at the core of the problem and it gives a clue about the reason for some response words occurrences in Word association tests (WAT). The experiment in the paper relies on data collection from testing students on their associations with 20 stimuli out of context. The focus is only on those stimulus words in which (near) homonymy is noticed. The suggested analysis is qualitative as the present paper interprets some particular cases from the experiment results rather than the overall situation in terms of quantity. Homonymy is considered in both Bulgarian and English languages as an act of delving a bit deeper into the reasons leading to confusion. The article addresses the relationship between mother tongue interference and artificial homonymy as a result of a word association test. Also, it relies on some findings in dictionaries of homonyms issued at different periods in time.*

Keywords: *association, homonymy, interference, phoneme.*

Introduction

It is widely admitted that the acquisition of a foreign language involves interference of mother tongue at different levels in the speech of any learner especially at an early stage. According to Aziz et al [3] mother tongue, native language and primary language bear the same meaning as first language does since it is natural that everyone gets acquainted with a language

*This work was supported by funding of a Shumen University project, *Digital Technologies in Teaching College Students*, № 08-61/ 24.01.2024.

little by little early in one's life. Mother tongue here is understood as referring to the language people learn from their mothers, "the speaker's dominant and home language" [17], but also as defined by Aziz et al. [3] to L1 "used in a society as a tool in communication". L1 interference occurs in literature as "transfer", "linguistic interference, and cross meaning" (ibid). Crystal [6] explains interference as a "negative transfer" and recognizes it as a term related to sociolinguistics and foreign-language learning to apply to the so called "errors a speaker introduces into one language as a result of contact with another language". He claims that the commonest source of error is related to mother tongue impeding the process of learning a foreign language.

Another definition that should be commented for the purpose of this paper is the term association. In "A Dictionary of Linguistics and Phonetics" [6] it is defined as the emotional associations which have to do with the connotation of a word that brings about another lexical item or a whole range of them on the basis of a psychological relation. They are referred to as word associations or sense associations. A similar view of the psycholinguistic term is offered by Sinopalnikova and Smrz [15] who describe it as the link between "ideas, concepts, or words, which exist in the human mind" where "an appearance of one entity entails the appearance of the other in the mind." According to Aitchison [1] memorizing is easier to achieve if information is well organized and the so called mental lexicon seems to be well structured as words are accessed "literally in a split second". Free association along with brainstorming or mind mapping can assist language learning and pave the way for students to cope with old and new knowledge on vocabulary more adequately building up relations between words.

Association words are easily gathered with the help of a Word association test (WAT) which is an experiment where the participants are offered words out of context one by one. To these stimuli the respondents are expected to react with whatever word comes first to their mind. WAT is related to the name of Francis Galton, who invented it and tried to test himself, and later with the names of Kent and Rosanoff, who conducted

a free association test in search of English language word association norms [16]. Although there is a relative variety of responses, reaction words tend to be repeated. These repetitions are considered significant for foreign language acquisition as they serve as a basis for identifying the norms which can be used for facilitating the process of lexis learning. They are valuable for language teaching since they present the picture in the human mind the way words are linked to each other. As the test has been used more than hundred years for purposes of different scientific fields, much has been written. Several types of relations are established in linguistic literature. In general, the semantic types comprise syntagmatic and paradigmatic relations where the former refers to words belonging to different parts of speech, and the latter is typical of same parts of speech. Among the semantic types Rahimi [11] uses other classes of association in his study. Some of them, due to the word form importance rather than meaning, are called formal. They are subdivided to phonological and orthographic types. From Sinopalnikova & Smrz' perspective [15] a small number of associations is formal and the majority of associations are semantic, i.e.: "caused by relations of objects in reality or respective concepts in the human mind." In the so called formal group they put associations that conjured up as a result of either phonetic or spelling similarity of words. Rahimi [11] also sees orthographic associations as counting on the shape of the word and understands phonological associations as relying on sound only, i.e. these are words that rhyme. According to him the latter have to do with the "clang" associations.

Before considering reaction words, it is necessary to mention a problem which might be compounded by the lack of clarity due to the free association format. As stimulus words are given out of context for some of the words the participants have to decide which one of the homonyms they are expected to react to. As stated by Beretta et al [4] homonymy is traditionally understood as "ambiguity between unrelated meanings ... where two words happen to share the same orthography and phonology". Rodd et al highlight that homonymy occurs less often

than another form of ambiguity known as polysemy [12]. This fact seems to make the matter a little less important but not less complicated.

Method

The approach in the research was qualitative as the aim was to describe the existing phenomenon the way it appeared in the conducted free association test without concentrating on precise numbers. Although the informants and answers were strictly kept into account, the paper was not to be understood as organized around quantitative analysis. Moreover, the focus was solely on an excerpt from the whole experiment. Only those stimulus words that received an obvious wrong interpretation were a subject of the research. The test was conducted several times in several successive years with the same 20 words and part of the results were analyzed in previous works [7, 8]. The present paper did not include those responses since stimuli were given in different circumstances during the pandemic years. The reaction words examined here pertain to the experiment in the last couple terms this year and were gathered as the same stimuli were read aloud in the presence of three small groups of participants at different time. An aural-written method was used for collecting data. The respondents were given a piece of paper with an empty table consisting of two columns where the students had to write the word or words that come first to their mind. All the stimulus words were read by the teacher in English. They were chosen as described in a previous paper [7]. The time for responding was set to approximately a minute but as the students gave indications of being ready, it turned out that they needed less than a minute to move on to the next stimulus word. Nevertheless, during the procedure of processing the collected data it became apparent that for a minority of respondents either the time was not enough to respond, or some other reason made them leave few of the spaces empty. However, it should not be mandatory the insufficient time to be indicated as a reason since everyone has their individual pace. A confirmation of it could be found in the secondary and even tertiary responses (all counted

as reaction words) that some of the rest of the respondents were able to give.

A twofold approach was undertaken. Firstly, the issue was studied in terms of homonymy in the Bulgarian language as compared to the English language, i.e what was considered to be a homophone and what phenomena in Bulgarian are different from those in the English phonetic system.

Secondly, the stimuli were looked up in English dictionaries of homonyms in order to make suggestions if there is an obvious link between the reaction words from the test and the listed homonyms. The suggested hypothesis about mother tongue influence was formed on the basis of the results.

Participants

The total number of informants was 29. Eleven of them identified themselves as beginners and the rest of them (62 per cent) wrote that they got familiar with the English language since attending kindergarten or studying at school. The range of their age was from 19 to 45, and the average age of all was calculated to 30-31. The younger ones were more fluent in English while those who left school many years ago were much more uncertain in their language abilities pointing out as a reason the lack of practice and negligence in terms of foreign language development during that long period before applying to college. All the participants were future primary school teachers.

Results

The aural-written format of the test does not assist production of orthographic associations. The identical situation allows to adopt Rahimi's [11] explanation as he underlines visual stimulation as a crucial factor for the natural activation of such associations. The experiment supplies a single example which could fall in this group, i.e bag as associated with bad. What remains to be considered as a subtype of the formal type of associations is the phonological one, where another single representative appeared, this time in the form of 'head' – 'had'

relation. The rest of the reaction words seem to be semantically associated.

Two of the used in the free association test stimuli are of interest for the present study. These are the words 'head' and 'bad'. Most of the responses are easily associated as natural reaction to the stimuli (e.g. 'hat' as one of the response words to 'head' was present in each of the results of WAT conducted during the years). Sometimes the respondents wrote their secondary and tertiary reaction words but all of them seemed relevant.

There are still other responses which, although really small in number, are to be mentioned to complete the whole picture of results. They comprise 4.3 per cent of the responses to this couple stimuli. Different reasons such as spelling and grammar mistakes may be identified as leading to these particular reactions. Apparently, while writing 'feadband', the respondent meant the word headband. 'Bader' is another inappropriate response which might be explained as grammatically incorrect formation of comparative degree to the respective adjective rather than the much less probable association with the British fighter pilot and national hero (see Collins online dictionary). Among some of the guesses about the response word 'bead' is the assumption that the respondent is familiar with the terminology of car mechanics where the words in syntagmatic relation in "bad bead" would mean that a tyre is damaged and needs to be fixed. Another hypothesis is the misspelling of the poker term 'bad beat' [20]. A third supposition is the reaction word to be a clang associate relying solely on sound similarity.

There is a minority group of primary answers which question the proper interpretation of what is heard, though. These responses are currently focused on and only they are listed below:

head – yellow, green, red, long, short, brown, had. Altogether they constitute 23 percent of the responses to this stimulus word.

bad - clean, room, bag, house, which make 17,4 per cent of all reaction words given to this stimulus.

Without going deep in neuroscience, it is useful to mention about two widespread models of language processing. Lukic et al [9] explain the access to the meaning of a word either as

“Exhaustive Access” which advocates the approach for context significance while all possible meanings are activated leaving space only to the appropriate ones, or as “Ordered Access” which proposes that interpretations are retrieved according to their frequency of usage. Although frequency is involved in a somewhat different context in their paper, the idea on the whole fits the case with free associations where no context is available to decide which one of the meanings to pick and react to. Frequency here is seen as a reflection of the language level of the tested students according to their coming across a particular word in the course of using the foreign language.

Discussion

The respondents in the conducted experiment with free associations supply information about the semantic fields being outlined on the one hand, and about the participants' level of sensitivity to the sounds in the foreign language, on the other. As Stoyanova [16] puts it, it is necessary for people to have knowledge about articulatory and acoustic features of a particular language in order to be able to produce messages. In the Bulgarian language the unstressed vowels are reduced regularly. Although the phonetic phenomenon called unstressed vocalism is typical for both Bulgarian and English, there are particular differences. According to Sabev and Andreeva's [14] conclusion from their experiment in Bulgarian the broad vowels /a, ɔ/ are narrowed and shortened in unstressed position and to the same values as those of /ɤ/ and /u/, which is claimed to be in conformity with the traditional view. As they find no changes in the narrow vowels /i, ɤ, u/ when unstressed, they refute the widespread opinion that these vowels broaden. As what concerns the last of the three vowels mentioned above the single difference they recognize is in the more frontal articulation of the unstressed /u/. Although, as pointed out by Pashova [10] the e→i reduction is absolutely unacceptable in formal Bulgarian, stress has a decisive role for the narrowing in the pronunciation of the Bulgarian vowels. The strongest reduction concerns indisputably the broad vowel /a/ which reminds the schwa sound in English.

Unfortunately, this narrowing valid for the Bulgarian unstressed vowels is not applicable to the stressed ones.

Therefore, another explanation of mother tongue interference credibility is to be suggested. As claimed by Stoyanova [16] devoicing voiced consonants at the end of the word is one of the first features that Bulgarian children learn about their language. On the other hand, in English, as stated by Walker, R. and Archer [18], “when voiced consonants come at the end of a word or a stressed syllable, they actually possess little or no voicing.” This means that the final noisy consonant sounds the way the final quiet consonant does. This seems to bring together the two languages in terms of the final consonants. But in English what makes the words different is due to the vowel before the last consonant which in case of a final voiced consonant is longer than it is before a final voiceless consonant. Walker and Archer (ibid.) claim that this “shortening effect of the voiceless consonant over the preceding vowel is true for all the voiceless consonants of English in almost all accents, and it is the principal way in which we can distinguish between *cap* and *cab*, *price* and *prize*, and so on”. This is completely untypical of the Bulgarian language where there is no variety of vowel length [2] and consequently it cannot have a dominant role in the meaning of a word in general. Unawareness of the existing difference between the native language and the foreign language might become a prerequisite for misinterpretation of the word being heard leaving room for mother tongue interference. Another thing the learners struggle with comes with the English vowels which do not exist in the Bulgarian language. The so called phonological sieve keeps the familiar sounds. This way the unfamiliar ones are left unnoticed or in a way converted into ordinary well known sounds. The influence of the mother tongue in this particular situation leads to confusion and in a kind infects with artificial homonymy which naturally splits the responses in at least two meanings.

In Bulgarian there is no absolute equivalence to the English /æ/ sound, and sometimes students make no difference between /æ/ and /e/ equating the former with the latter. The lack

of the correspondence between the English /æ/ vowel and any other vowel in Bulgarian as well as the tendency the final voiced consonants to become voiceless in Bulgarian direct the pairs head – hat and bad – bed/ bat to be regarded as nearly phonetic homonyms for the students who study English. The interference has an impact on recognition and interpretation of the English words that are heard.

Another means of explicating the results from the WAT as a consequence of the mother tongue interference is while relying on dictionaries of English homonyms. The Dictionary of Homonyms [13] gives the past tense of the word bid as the homonym of bad. It is clarified that only one of the two acceptable pronunciation forms of the word is to be considered for the purpose. It says that in past tense it “can be pronounced with a short ‘a’, in which case it is a homophone for ‘bad’, or with a long ‘a’, in which case, of course, it isn’t.” Unfortunately, this is not quite in conformity with Walker and Archer’s arguments [18] for cab and cap.

Further discrepancies come with another dictionary. More than hundred years earlier ‘A Dictionary of English Homonyms’ designed to help foreigners manage to learn words ‘very similar in sound but differently spelled, and conveying different meanings’ gave a variety of other words defined as homonyms of bad, i. e. bat, pad, pat [5].

As the response words seem to have nothing in common with the associations that the homophones from these dictionaries would most probably arise, it could be assumed that the respondents were influenced by their mother tongue. As long as this assumption is not supported by any data, such an assertion is only a hypothesis and a future WAT on bat, pad, and pat would either confirm or reject it.

Although orthographically different due to the pronunciation peculiarities of the Bulgarian language such pairs as the listed below [19] are considered to be homophones:

- “шев и шеф” (shev and shef)
- “под и пот” (pod and pot)
- “куб и куп” (kub and kup)

- “кос и коз” (kos and koz)

The list of homonyms for the word ‘bad’ from Bey’s dictionary allows to conclude that not only if the last voiced consonant is replaced by voiceless one it is accepted as a homonym but also in case of the first consonant at the beginning of the word, which seems unacceptable for the Bulgarian language. On the other hand, Rothwell’s dictionary, as pointed out to be issued more than hundred years later, offers only one homonym of the same word concerning the vowel, which gives some kind of evidence to suggest that things might have changed with time. This definitely does not indicate that the old dictionary cannot be trusted since other examples (e.g. ‘hat’ is given as a homonym of ‘had’ [5] confirm what is given in the newly released book on pronunciation by Walker and Archer [18]. The latter emphasizes the significance of vowel length, quite similar to what was said in Bey’s dictionary in terms of the homonym of bad being pointed out.

Along with syntagmatic and paradigmatic associations in her classification for the Bulgarian language Stoyanova [16] places associations according to sound similarity such as „град – грах; влак – мрак; време- бreme; дума – гума и т.н.“ (grad – grah; vlak – mrak; vreme – breme; дума – гума, etc.) Such a type of association occurs in the English language as well and it is generally known as clang association. An example of this type from the experiment is the word ‘bag’ as a response word to ‘bad’. This could be interpreted as orthographic mother tongue interference because of the letter ‘g’ in Bulgarian which sounds as /d/ but looks like the letter ‘g’ in English.

The words ‘clean’, ‘room’, and ‘house’ that were written by the respondents reveal eloquently the connections they make between these reaction words and the word ‘bed’ instead of the stimulus ‘bad’. The importance of the vowel features might be the reason for the absence of the word head in the above commented dictionaries of homonyms in English.

There weren’t any discussions with the students after the test to have the chance to explain what they meant while writing the responses. Therefore, some cases are difficult to decide

whether these fall into the group of true associations or should be excluded because the stimulus word is misunderstood. The way human anatomy allows for word combinations such as 'long head' and 'short head' in terms of biceps, hats are also possible to be short or long. There is similar uncertainty about the response word 'brown' which could be associated with 'head' but more naturally it is to be referred to a 'hat'. It should be guessed whether the response words yellow, red and green are responses to misinterpreted word 'hat' instead of head. On the other hand, there is a certain possibility for these answers to be appropriately used as associated to Asians, Native Americans and an emoji on the Internet, respectively.

The suggested homonyms in these dictionaries and the reaction words given by the respondents, who took part in the WAT, offer the opportunity for making comparisons and certain inferences.

Conclusions

The final conclusion concerns the great influence of mother tongue but only in a couple of instances. It is only two of the 20 stimuli that create appropriate conditions for homonymous words to emerge in students' mind and stir associations different from what is generally expected.

As Stoyanova [16] points out, building up language specific articulation and acoustic automatic behavior is typical for L1, while with the second and any one further acquired it is extremely rare to achieve. Bearing this in mind the role of foreign language teacher is significant in drawing the attention of the students to such specificities, and this is crucial to the prevention of mother tongue interference.

There seems to be enough reasons to conclude that in terms of homonymy the quality of produced vowels is more important in English than in Bulgarian. Therefore, some of the tested in free associations Bulgarian students ignored the significance of English vowel sounds which naturally led to wrong interpretation of the word which on its part evoked quite different associations. Noteworthy, knowledge about differences in

phonology of the two languages would reduce artificial examples of homonymy and this way help students grapple to some extent with the difficulties that stem from homonymous words.

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